

USING PODCAST IN ENHANCING THE ORAL PROFICIENCY AMONG GRADE 9 STUDENTS OF SAN PEDRO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine if using podcast can help students enhance their oral proficiency in terms of pronunciation, intonation, word stress and vowel sounds. The following are the compelling objectives of the study: 1) determine the pre-test scores of the respondents before their podcast exposure in terms of: intonation; pronunciation; vowel sounds; and word stress, 2) find out the post-test scores of the respondents after listening to podcast in terms of: pronunciation; intonation; word stress; and vowel sounds, and 3) assess the scores in oral proficiency assessment. Data were collected from 30 Grade 9 students at San Pedro National High School in which experimental research was utilized. Consequently, percentage score and paired T-test were used to treat the data. Results showed that majority of the students are classified under the novice and intermediate categories in the pre-test assessment in speaking while on the post-test, most students were considered as advanced speakers. This is demonstrated based on the obtained scores in the assessment. Furthermore, the results emphasized that there is a significant difference between the use of podcast and oral proficiency related variables. Podcast listening can aid students remedy their problems in pronunciation, intonation, word stress and vowel sounds. By being exposed with how a certain language is uttered, stressed, and enunciated, students will be able to incorporate it in their speech. Meanwhile, podcast listening can provide enough time for students to practice their skills in speaking on a slower pace. In general, given the availability of podcast technology, and students being digital natives, podcast usage is one of many ways they can improve their speaking ability that is not only educational but also something that is tailored fit to their interests.

Keywords: language and teaching, podcast, oral proficiency, experimental study, Philippines